

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

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Sample Name: Proszki

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Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

- C K
- O K
- SiK

C K_ROI (73)

O K_ROI (31)

Si K_ROI (64)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 16.16 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	26.3	0.04	44.3	1090.6	10.2
O K	5.1	0.02	6.4	849.9	7.3
Si K	68.6	0.02	49.3	8662.9	5.6